

Inconsistency of \mathbb{N}

Enrico P. G. Cadeddu *

15 January 2026

Abstract

Inconsistency of the actual infinity, thus \mathbb{N} , follows from the strict inclusion of the natural numbers in ω , but also by considering the chain of infinitely many terms $\frac{1}{n}$ and 0.

$\omega \equiv (0, 1, 2, 3, 4, \dots)$ and each number $n \in \omega$ ($n \in \mathbb{N}$) is the subset: $(0, 1, 2, 3, 4, \dots, n-1)$.

$$0 \subset 1 \subset 2 \subset \dots \subset n \subset \dots \subset \omega \tag{1}$$

(1) represents $\omega + 1$. ω is greater than any finite number n , it contains more elements (numbers) than those contained in any n , $\forall n(n < \omega) \quad |\omega| = \aleph_0$. There is no natural number equal to ω , $\forall n(n < \omega) \rightarrow \nexists n(n = \omega)$.

A representation of (1) is this:

Figure 1

It follows from (1) that there exists at least one element of ω that does not belong to any n ; $\exists x \in \omega \forall n(n \leq x)$. $\{(0) (1) (2) (3) (4) \dots x\}$; " $\{ \}$ " delimit ω and " $()$ " delimit each of its proper subsets n . This is absurd.

Assuming x is not present, only numbers n occur before " $\}$ ", and nothing else, thus only

* Email Address cadeddu.e@gmail.com

subsets. Even if there is no specific number that immediately precedes "}", there must nevertheless exist a subset before "}". This is equivalent to: $\{(0) (1) (2) (3) (4) \dots\}$. But "}" implies that at least one n is not a proper subset of ω , hence: $\exists n(n = \omega)$, a contradiction. $(x \rightarrow \perp) \rightarrow \neg x$, $(\neg x \rightarrow \perp) \rightarrow \neg\neg x$; $\neg x \wedge \neg\neg x$.

Another approach is the following. By comparing each n with ω , element by element, $f : n \rightarrow \omega$, it is seen that infinitely many elements of ω are not used.

For the Axiom of Infinity, all natural numbers exist simultaneously. The actual infinity is being considered.

Nothing prevents simultaneously comparing all n with ω . Thus: $f : 0 \rightarrow \omega$, $f : 1 \rightarrow \omega$, $f : 2 \rightarrow \omega$, $f : 3 \rightarrow \omega$, $f : 4 \rightarrow \omega$... $f : n \rightarrow \omega$, All numbers are considered (it is equivalent to: $\bigcup_{n \in \mathbb{N}} n = \mathbb{N}$), thus with this simultaneous comparison, **all elements (numbers) of ω are used**.

But this comparison, of all n with ω , must also take (1) into account; consequently, **at least one element of ω is not used**, as it can be deduced in the triangular scheme in Figure 2 (conversely figures 1 and 2 imply (1)). This is a contradiction.

Figure 2

Geometrically, the clearest proof is the following. A line segment is composed of infinitely many points. Consider an infinite countable subset of these points, uniformly distributed along the segment and all indexed. This can be done by considering all the rational numbers obtained by dividing the line segment 0—1 into n parts and taking all n : $\bigcup_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \{\frac{k}{n} : k = 0, 1, 2, \dots, n\}$.

It is clear that any given point, corresponding to a natural number m , must be preceded by a finite number of points, equal to m . By making the appropriate geometric proportions, the number of points that follow it is also finite; for instance, consider a point at the center of the segment $|\text{---} \cdot_m \text{---}|$. Therefore, the quantity of the countable points of the segment is finite, a contradiction.

But it would not be possible to perform an indexing in this way, because a rational number immediately following 0 (or any other rational number) would not exist.

This classical impossibility is avoided by not forgetting the actual infinity, that is a complete totality (time-independent), and considering the point of view of "0" (in this lies the geometric feature): if there were no immediate successor of "0", then from the perspective of "0" (one-dimensional) there would be unobservable points (rational numbers) preceding the one that is observed, or no point would be observed.

Alternatively, ω (in Figure 2) can be considered as corresponding to an infinite segment, with natural numbers equally spaced by a finite distance.

Proof

First, the existence of (1) is proved. All natural numbers exist, for the Axiom of Infinity, and then all successors exist. There are infinitely many successors, and they are:

$$(\quad) + 1) + 1) + 1) + 1) + \dots \tag{2}$$

with a successor, thus a natural number, enclosed by each pair of parentheses. (2) is equivalent to: $0_0 + 1_1 + 1_2 + 1_3 + 1_4 + \dots$. This sum is given by a transfinite ordinal sum, which uses the disjoint union together with the order. The transfinite ordinal sum can be considered the formal representation of (2) and (1).

Thus (2) is equal to ω (the simple disjoint union, without considering the order, would give \aleph_0). Every finite sum in (2) defines a number belonging to ω . Hence, (2) \equiv (1), (1) exists. " $\subset \omega$ " is imposed by the ordinal nature of ω itself.

In (1), before the symbol " $\subset \omega$ ", there must be a natural number, an unknown number q ; because " \subset " **refers to two sets, in this case a number q and ω** . Thus the "last term" q (its existence would already be a contradiction) is imposed by the order relation " \subset ". Hence, there exists at least one element of ω that does not belong to q , and consequently to any n . But each natural number must be an element of another natural number, thus a contradiction.

It is possible to prove (1) in a simple way referring to Figure 3, in which $\forall n \ n \subset \omega$ is represented. Given the chain of inclusions, it is not necessary to specify $n \subset \omega$ for each n to affirm $\forall n \ n \subset \omega$, because it is sufficient to consider $n + 1 \subset \omega \ (\rightarrow n \subset \omega)$. This makes it possible to prove (1) by induction. Thus, the inductive step is this: $n \subset \omega$ is not necessary because $n \subset n + 1 \subset \omega$, but then $n + 1 \subset \omega$ is not necessary either, since $n + 2 \subset \omega$ ($n \subset n + 1$ implies $n + 1 \subset n + 2$ because $n < n + 1$ implies $n + 1 < n + 2$). $\forall m > l \ (m \subset \omega) \rightarrow \forall n \ n \subset \omega$, thus it is not necessary to refer to $l - 1$, and therefore not to l either. Hence, no " $\subset \omega$ " in Figure 3 is necessary, and (1) follows; since the presence of " $\subset \omega$ " is in any case required at least at the end of the chain.

Figure 3

In an even simpler way, ω closes the chain because the transitivity property holds for ordinals, so the final term must be " $\subset \omega$ ".

Finally, consider the chain: $0 < \dots < \frac{1}{n} < \dots < \frac{1}{4} < \frac{1}{3} < \frac{1}{2} < 1$. For the Axiom of Infinity all numbers $\frac{1}{n}$ must be present. " 0 " has no immediate successor; that is, between 0 and any other number there exists another number. But, in the chain, in an actual sense, " $0 <$ " implies an immediately following number. Hence this chain is incomplete, it does not exist infinitely; infinitely many numbers must be missing immediately after 0 . This appears as a clear contradiction of the Axiom of Infinity rather than something normal to accept, especially since, once all the numbers are given, their ordering is a spontaneous and intrinsic fact. And there is no reason why many numbers should disappear in the ordering.

Figure 4

The following question can also be considered. Can it be asserted that 0 has no immediate successor — thus that there is no “gap” (a gap: no number between 0 and its successor) — without admitting the existence of some number $\frac{1}{n}$ at an infinitesimal or zero distance from 0 ? It cannot be so.

In fact, all numbers of the chain " $\frac{1}{n}$ " exist simultaneously, and no number lie at an infinitesimal distance from 0 . Then there exists a finite distance Δx separating 0 from the chain. Thus, other numbers of the chain lie within this distance. This yields a contradiction: not all numbers of the chain exist simultaneously.

On the other hand, it can be shown that this finite distance Δx does not exist (given a number, there is always another one), and hence that an infinitesimal distance would imply the absurd result of a number of the chain lying at an infinitesimal distance from 0 .

More precisely, $\nexists n : (0, \frac{1}{n}) = \emptyset$, then 0 is not immediately succeeded by an empty interval. This may simply imply: $(0, \frac{1}{n}) \neq \emptyset \forall n$, that is, there is at least one point between 0 and $\frac{1}{n}$. But, considering all the terms of the chain simultaneously, and thus wishing to represent them in a single “static picture” (as the actuality of the infinite would require), what would one see? A $\Delta x = 0$ between 0 and a $\frac{1}{n}$. Thus a contradiction, because $\frac{1}{n} \neq 0$ (or $\neq dx$).

Furthermore, consider the sum: $1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + \dots = (1 - 0) + (2 - 1) + (3 - 2) + (4 - 3) + (5 - 4) + \dots + (n - (n - 1)) + \dots$. This sum is equal to ω , but there are only natural numbers, which cancel out in pairs (1 with -1 , 2 with -2 and so on). However, not all terms must cancel, since it can be reduced to a sum of 1 (thus > 0); therefore, at least one term must remain, an n . This implies a number $n = \omega$, a contradiction. The residual of the cancellations, n , ensures the equivalence between the sum of the 1 's and the sum of the terms after cancellations, since the residual balances the cancellations (would this avoid the inapplicability of certain rules for finite sums to infinite ones?).

Conclusion

This proof is certainly valid from an infinitary standpoint, that is, if one admits (1) precisely as an infinite string. (1) is not syntactically correct in ZF set theory (although it can be defined in ZF), but it should be verified whether (1) is nevertheless completely described, in all its parts and interrelations, within ZF.

Furthermore, it should be noted that in geometry, a segment, or a line, is an object composed of infinitely many points, in which a countable subset of points can be indexed. Therefore, the infinite string, and in general the natural numbers, can be represented by a geometric (semantic) model (as in figures 1, 2 and the consideration about the line segment). All models of $\omega + 1$ share the same underlying order and are isomorphic as ordinals (set-theoretic model is: $(\omega \cup \{\omega\}, \in)$). Any ordinal property (such as succession, \in , maximum, initial segments, etc.) that holds in one model holds in all others. Hence, no model of $\omega + 1$ is consistent; $\omega + 1$ is inconsistent and in the theory of ordinals, ω is also inconsistent (the consideration about the line segment directly involves ω).